

Morphosyntactic Analysis of Cypriot Turkish-English Codeswitching: Agglutination of Embedded Lexemes and Bilingual Periphrastic VP Creations

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Abstract. This study investigates agglutination and periphrasis in bilingual noun phrases (NPs) and verb phrases (VPs) when codeswitching between agglutinative Cypriot Turkish and synthetic English. The focus is on English elements embedded in Cypriot Turkish to assess adherence to the morphosyntactic rules of the Matrix Language (Myers-Scotton, 2006). Drawing on the 4M-Model (Myers-Scotton, 2006) and Boumans' (2007) analysis of bilingual VP patterns, the research examines the morphosyntactic behavior in Cypriot Turkish-English codeswitching, diverging from previous studies on Turkish-English pairings (Koban, 2013; Kemaloglu-Er, 2018). The study uses data from 90 minutes of semi-structured conversations with young Cypriot Turkish-English speakers, yielding 143 tokens of codeswitching, 49% of which were intra-sentential. Contrary to Poplack's (1980) claim that embedded words appear in bare forms, 57% of embeddings were agglutinated with up to two suffixes for nouns/adjectives and up to four for verbs. Predominant morphemes included Turkish dative, accusative, and pluralization suffixes, as well as possessive inflections. Bilingual VPs, comprising 18% of the tokens, often utilized periphrasis (61%) with light verbs such as "yap" (make), "et" (do), and "ol" (be). Embedded verbs also featured verb-making suffixes like "-le(mek)" (to do) and "-dı" (to be.PST). The findings largely support the MFL and 4M-Model, highlighting a correlation between intense language contact and periphrastic verb formations. Additionally, Cypriot Turkish shows similarities with Cypriot Greek rather than Turkic languages, with codeswitches behaving like assimilated lexical borrowings. This research underscores the role of codeswitching as an identity-building tool among young Cypriot Turkish-English bilinguals, reflecting their positive attitude towards bilingualism.

Keywords: Cypriot Turkish; bilingualism; codeswitching; morphosyntax; periphrasis; agglutination

1 Introduction

The morphological-syntactic regulations of codeswitching have been frequently studied and enriched through the study of morphosyntactic combinations of various languages with different typologies. A fruitful language pairing for studying codeswitching between is the suffix-dominated agglutinative Turkish, and the more simplistic/fusional lingua franca English, which this essay aims to investigate on morpho-syntactic grounds. The structural properties of codeswitching outlined by Poplack (1980) with the Free Morpheme and Equivalence Constraint, and later by Myers-Scotton's (2006) Matrix Language Frame (MFL) and 4M Model provide theoretical patterns for such bilingual combinations, with ample research testing their findings. Not enough attention, however, has been paid within the literature to agglutination and inflectional patterns of codeswitched words and phrases within this pairing. Therefore, this paper aims to address this gap in research by studying codeswitching patterns of bilingual speakers of Cypriot Turkish and English.

In her research on codeswitching habits of Turkish-English bilinguals in New York, Koban's (2013) findings avoid evaluation of the agglutination patterns of codeswitching by only studying the differentiation between intra- and inter-sentential switches, with the intra-sentential switches being categorised into single-word and double-word categories depending on how many L2 words the

speakers preferred to embed into their L1 in each utterance. Similarly, although Kemaloğlu-Er (2018) highlighted postpositional Turkish structures appearing within prepositional English forms, disproving Poplack's Free Morpheme Constraint that suggests bound morphemes like affixes cannot be embedded into another language, the researcher mentions very little about bilingual constructions that form complex multilingual morpheme/word clusters, going against the Free Morpheme Constraint. Turkish being a highly agglutinative language, 'nonce words' (Poplack, 1980) or embedded words are likely to receive multiple inflections even before being phonologically and morphologically integrated into the Matrix Language Frame (Myers-Scotton, 2006), which is the dominant model of language into which embeddings from a L2 are inserted. Therefore, while it is possible to come across English embedded words in their bare forms within Turkish phrases, they might also receive complex inflections from the Matrix language, under Myers-Scotton's 4M-model.

Moreover, in the case of embedded verbs from English into Turkish, the literature shows either a noun-to-verb agglutination process between the two languages, or a bilingual periphrasis function that combines the embedded verb/island with an auxiliary verb or catena from the Matrix structure, as further demonstrated later in Findings. Boumans (2007) points these two phenomena out, positing that the latter form can be regarded as a marker of intense language contact. Interestingly, Boumans' cross-linguistic analysis of these periphrastic formations provides a comparison of Cypriot Greek's high use of periphrasis in codeswitching and borrowings against Mainland Greek's use, stating that 'in 1960 Cyprus gained independence [as a British colony] and (Modern Standard) Greek became the language of administration. The English language remained influential through the tourism industry and the large international community on the island' (2007, p.300). While the researcher uses this in relation to intense language contact, Boumans fails to consider that the official languages of the Republic of Cyprus are Greek, along with Turkish and English. The intense contact formations, therefore, should be equally likely to appear in the island's second native language, which this essay's Turkish-speaking Cypriot sample, who speak Cypriot dialects of Turkish, and are all from backgrounds that value English's usefulness in inter- and intra-communal communications, will provide further evidence on. With these considered, the main questions of research emerge as:

1. Do English embedded lexemes receive multiple or complex Turkish inflections?
2. Do codeswitched Turkish VPs with English verbs occur more with periphrasis than inflections (perhaps due to intense language contact between Cypriot Turkish and English)?

Using the findings of Boumans and Myers-Scotton's updated MFL, we can hypothesise that the answers to both questions will be more on the affirmative side, given the linguistic characteristics of Turkish as a matrix language. While testing this speculation, this essay also aims to consider these questions along with the data produced with consideration of participant language attitudes towards codeswitching, for more wholistic speaker profiles.

2 Methods

To study these within limitations of time and brevity, the study was conducted with four participants chosen using a purposive sampling method. The specific speaker characteristics sought for are further discussed in the following section. The design of the study consisted of two one-hour semi-structured conversation sessions moderated by the researcher, with two separate, randomly-assigned speaker pairs. Before the sessions, all participants signed consent forms, and were given an overview of their right to withdraw, with any arising questions answered by the researcher without any leading answers. The pairs in the sessions were allocated randomly, but since all speakers were picked from the same broad social

group in Cyprus, they all had previous connections with each other. This assured that the participants were quicker to start a relaxed conversation, thus providing natural instances of codeswitching. As emphasised by Koban's (2013) design, the research tried to capture codeswitching between Cypriot Turkish-English bilinguals from the same social background as an unmarked speech variety that occurs organically within this wider community of Turkish-speaking Cypriot young-adults. Hence, although the researcher was an active listener within the conversations, only a few open-ended questions were provided to generate some discussions about language attitudes. This study design was also observed in Eversteijn's (2011) study on Turkish-Dutch bilingual teenagers, who highlighted the advantages of open-ended questions in groups of 2-4 participants, suggesting that 'informants started to compare and complement each other's answers.' Therefore, while the natural conversation of friends and organic occurrences of codeswitching were prioritised, a finer social profile of the speakers were created considering their discussions to better understand the function of codeswitching within their speech community.

The two sessions took place over video chat to stimulate a friendly online conversation space, generating about two hours of data. The first 45 minutes of each conversation were studied, and all occurrences of codeswitching, along with instances of syntactic mishaps, incoherence, or ungrammaticality caused by a mismatch between the two competing language structures, were transcribed and tabulated by the researcher. During transcriptions, the codeswitching tokens were separated into groups of intra-sentential, inter-sentential, and an additional category of 'extra-sentential' for tag interjections after Poplack (1980). While the intra-sentential switches were counted as L2 embeddings on single word or NP levels, the inter-sentential group consisted of CP-level switches. The third category was made to differentiate the more solidified forms of phrasal codeswitches that were referential to Anglophone internet culture such as well-known quotes from Vine, Tiktok, or collocations. Further distinctions were made between 'intra-clausal' (Myers-Scotton, 2006) morphological embeddings to look at the number of suffixes they received; and agglutinated/non-agglutinated VP structures to look at the suffixes accompanying the embedded verbs or catenae used for periphrasis, to help with coding. The participants were informed that this research was focused on codeswitching habits within their community, which was discussed in conversation amongst them, but were not given any definite cues as to what aspects of codeswitching were being studied and codified. The participants were allowed to start their sentences in any language they preferred throughout the session, and the moderator did not prompt the use of a specific language during the conversations. Therefore, while most recorded instances of codeswitching were English embedded word and islands within Cypriot Turkish matrix clauses, some instances such as reported speech codeswitches were with sentences that were formed in the English matrix frame.

3 Sample

As mentioned, the sample of this study were all chosen because they were from the same social circle of Turkish-speaking Cypriot teenagers in their early twenties. The intensity of language contact that can explain their codeswitching patterns is observed through their reports of multilingual living. All speakers had Turkish-speaking Cypriot parents with varying degrees of bilingualism within the immediate family. Three speakers, coded *I*, *B*, and *C*, received their secondary education in a private English school for both Greek-speaking and Turkish-speaking Cypriots, where the education was predominantly in English. One speaker, coded *A*, went to a Turkish-English grammar school, where Turkish was relatively used more frequently in administration and classrooms. While the former group report higher usages of codeswitching within the Turkish-speaking Cypriot (TsC) youth at school, *A* states only a few people frequently codeswitched during conversations outside classrooms. More

importantly, all participants are currently pursuing their higher education within the UK and have an advanced English proficiency from utilising it in their social, educational, and professional lives. Naturally, codeswitching is more common in speech amongst people from the same community who also study in the UK.

Moreover, the language attitudes measured by the participants' conversations springing from open-ended questions suggest that codeswitching within this community is a matter of comfort and 'unmarkedness' (Myers-Scotton, 1983). All speakers recognise that codeswitching outside of their community's discourses serves to create emphasis and acknowledge the difference of other bilingual varieties such as those of the Cypriot diasporas from their form of codeswitching arising from years of English education and mass media consumption, which suggests the forms studied could be more individualistic. The speakers emphasised that they explicitly codeswitch with a specific friend group, and the importance of (specifically Cypriot) Turkish for their social identities, highlighting their feeling of responsibility to keep their L1 'alive'. While the following discussions consider language contact and proficiency in both languages as an explanation for the phenomena studied, future researchers might want to conduct a more impressionistic study by focusing on other sociolinguistic factors such as age, class, socio-political identity development, etc. in relation to codeswitching in Cyprus.

4 Findings

Within 90 minutes of speech recorded between *B&I* and *A&C*, 143 tokens of codeswitching were collected. Five of these instances were ruled out from the following analysis for being syntactic errors in monolingual sentences (direct translations of phrases, wrong word order, etc.), but recorded for signalling non-selective activation. Of the total amount, 78% of codeswitches were single or phrase-level nouns, adjectives, tag insertions, and TP/CP level inter-sententials. The breakdown of the classifications of these codeswitches are represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pie chart depicting the percentages of the classifications of recorded codeswitching tokens (excluding VP- level embedding), $N=111$.

Most of the non-VP-level codeswitches were “intra-clausal” (Myers-Scotton, 2006), with extra- and intra-sententials occurring on word or phrase-levels. The majority of the extra-sentential codeswitches recorded were phrase insertions such as ‘*oh my God, o zaman iyi para alın*’ (meaning ‘*oh my God, then you are getting good money*’), and word-level fillers like ‘literally’, ‘obviously’. The majority of the recorded inter-sententials were English embedded phrases within a Turkish Matrix Frame and were marked by a complementiser discourse marker (functioning as a content morpheme (Myers-Scotton, 2006)) such as ‘*yani*’ (‘*so*’) or ‘*like*’, (see Example (1), spoken by *C*), or a slight pause.

(1) Turkish-English

yani it's seen as like demeaning; gendi kültür -ün -ü bil -me -n
so <it's seen as like demeaning>, own culture -2SG.POSS -ACC know -NEG -2SG
'I mean **it's seen as like demeaning**; you do not know your own culture.'

Importantly, of the recorded intra-sentential codeswitches, 38 tokens were lexical borrowings, and 16 were NP structures like “government building”, “advanced research centre”, etc. These were the tokens observed to study the complexity of agglutination and number of affixes, producing Figure 2.

Figure 2: Percentages of bare and agglutinated embedded words and Noun Phrases, differentiating the number of added suffixes, $N=54$.

It was found that suffixation of embedded words happens more frequently, however a standard pattern for single, double, or more suffixation was not observed. In embedded lexemes and NPs, the most suffixes received were two. The most used suffixes were the dative (-e/-a such as in ‘grammar-a’, ‘to the grammar’) and accusative cases (-ı/-i/-u/-ü such as in ‘o line-ı okuduğumda’, ‘when I read that line’), along with pluralisation (-ler/-lar in ‘sexuality-ler’, ‘sexualities’). On double suffixed words, these were usually followed by a possessive (see Ex. 2, spoken by A).

(2) Turkish

el gol hareket -ler -im ə:: expression-lar-un da
hand arm movement -PL -1SG.POSS ə:: <expression>-PL-1SG.POSS too
değiş -me -(y)e başla-r.
change -INF -DAT start-PRS
'my hand-arm movements, uhh, my **expressions** start to change too.'

In the case of verbs and VP-level codeswitches that formed 18% of the total score of tokens, agglutination happened with up to 4 suffixes. These tokens that are not represented in Figure 1 show

that the bilingual VPs formed with agglutination used either the N-to-V suffix ‘-le(mek)’, ‘(to) do’, or ‘-dı’, ‘to be.(PST)’, along with regular inflectional morphemes showing person, tense, and negation, such as in Example 3 uttered by *I*:

- (3) Turkish
submit -le -di -(y)di -m
 <submit> -do -PST -IPVF -1SG

These forms of VPs only formed 31% of the bilingual verb and VP-level formations, with the majority being formed with periphrasis using Turkish auxiliary catenae, or ‘light verbs’ (Alexiadou, 2011) such as ‘yap(mak)’, ‘(to) make’, ‘et(mek)’, ‘(to) do’, or ‘ol(mak)’, ‘(to) be’ (see Fig. 3). In periphrastic forms, the embedded verbs retained their bare form, while the catenae were agglutinated, and as depicted, periphrasis was preferred more when embedding verbs into speech. Most bilingual VP creations preferred periphrasis with the light verb meaning *to make*, as exemplified by the gloss in Example 4 uttered by *B*.

- (4) Turkish
Hayir, düşün-dü -m ve relate yap -dı -m!
 No think -PST -1SG and <relate> make -PST -1SG
 ‘No, I thought about it, and **I relate to it!**’

Figure 3: Percentages of Verb Phrases formulated with embedded verbs and agglutination or periphrasis, with the additional distinction of auxiliary verbs used in the latter, N=26.

5 Discussion

Recalling the two research questions as:

1. Do English embedded lexemes receive multiple or complex Turkish inflections? and
2. Do codeswitched Turkish VPs with English verbs occur more with periphrasis than inflections?,

the results seem to provide mostly affirmative answers. Although not enough data is gathered to pass a rigid judgement about the ‘complexity’, it is seen that embedded words do get agglutinated under the Matrix Language’s regulations instead of remaining in simple (bare) forms, proving that the Matrix Language descends even into the morphological units of the Embedded Language (Myers-Scotton, 2006). This observed infiltration reflects the much-discussed dilemma between embeddings and borrowings, which tread the line of inseparability due to their high-level integration (Poplack & Dion, 2012; Myers-Scotton, 2006). The high number of extrasentential tags and multiple-worded collocational intra-/inter-sentential switches (see Fig. 1) also affirm Myers-Scotton’s theory about the larger fragments or islands of Embedded Language remaining intact to avoid the constraints of the Matrix Language (2006), as their structures were mostly retained due to speakers syntactically manoeuvring around them, as evident in Example 1. Moreover, the distinction of extra-sententials during coding highlighted the effect of social media, and networks utilising an English sociolect which emphasises the importance of referential internet culture, on the codeswitching habits of the speakers. Although Melado & Lignos (2022) state that abbreviations like “OMG” were particles from a not-necessarily-bilingual ‘internet dialect’, the sample’s codeswitches definitely accentuated these utterances and hinted at a sociolinguistic purpose for this form of codeswitching within this community of speakers. Codeswitching in general, whether Turkish-to-English or vice versa, seems to have an additional sociolinguistic role within the bilingual Cypriot community, as speakers reported that they also inserted Cypriot Turkish into their English as an act of identity building and preservation.

In terms of intra-sentential codeswitches being preferred more, the findings coincide with Koban’s (2013) hypothesis that advanced bilinguals are more likely to codeswitch intrasententially, since the sample were proficient in both languages from an early age (see Sample). However, the groups’ familiarity and recognition of each other’s proficiencies did not influence the complexity of suffixation of embedded nouns, adjectives, and NP’s, since embeddings did not receive that many early or late system morphemes, as predicted by Myers-Scotton’s 4M-Model (2006). Excluding verbs and VPs, embedded words received a maximum of 2 suffixes, which, when compared to matrix noun suffixations (see ‘hareket-lerim’ and ‘expression-lar-ım’ in Ex. 2), does not appear particularly dense. Here, we also see Kemalöglu-Er’s (2018) results affirmed, and Poplack’s Free Morpheme Constraint (1980) debunked once again, as speakers used English free morphemes with Turkish bound morphemes regularly.

In relation to periphrasis and intense language contact, the results were mostly supportive of Boumans’ (2007) statements. Although Boumans suggested that Turkic languages use periphrasis in ‘virtually all language contact situations’, some noteworthy forms of agglutinative bilingual verb-formation were also observed. His assertion concerning Cypriot Greek either applying complete morphological integration to embedded verbs with ‘ML axes’, or using periphrasis with auxiliary ‘light verbs’ (Alexiadou, 2011; see Ex. 4) to be inflected instead of the embedded verb, seems to apply more correctly to Cypriot Turkish as well. Considering the sample as representative for the community of young Turkish-speaking Cypriots who use English inter- and intra-communally, the hypothesis that intense language contact results in more observations of bilingual periphrasis is supported to an extent (see Fig. 3). Similarly, the structures of verb-creating agglutination were preceded by Alexiadou (2011), who stated that embedded verbs were only through ‘indirect insertion’ after a N-to-V class-changing suffix was applied first. This is exemplified by the use of the highly productive verb-forming suffix ‘-le(mek)’ as a bordering affix, allowing further inflection only after ‘changing the category’ of the

embedded verb (see Ex. 3). These forms of bilingual VP-creation signify both the advanced proficiencies of the speakers in both languages, along with the intensity of language contact and codeswitching within their daily communications. Furthermore, the choices of embedded lexemes suggest that codeswitching resulted from certain semantic fields being acquired only in one language. All participants noted the absence of some subject-specific terms in Turkish, and English academic jargon's irreplaceable 'naturalness'.

Overall, through studying the morphosyntax of codeswitching of Cypriot Turkish-English bilingual young-adults, the study yields intriguing data in support of a positive correlation between bilingual periphrasis and intense language contact as posited by Boumans (2007), and interesting agglutination patterns observed on embedded words, in line with Myers-Scotton's 4M-Model (2006). Within this social group, positive language attitudes towards the phenomenon are observed within the sample, reflecting that English embeddings are not seen as deformative, but a sociolinguistic identity-building tool that should be researched further, with the speakers using the two languages to fill in the semantic gaps.

Finally, while the design of the study might have caused biases such as an observer's paradox, organic instances of codeswitching were captured by the researcher, that represent the natural intra-communal utilisation of codeswitching within the young community of Cypriot Turkish-English bilinguals.

6 References

- Alexiadou, A. (2011). Remarks on the morpho-syntax of code-switching. *Proceedings of the 9th international Conference on Greek Linguistics*, 44–55.
- Boumans, L. (2007). The periphrastic bilingual verb construction as a marker of intense language contact. Evidence from Greek, Portuguese and Maghribian Arabic. In E. Ditters & H. Motzki (Eds.), *Approaches to Arabic linguistics* (pp. 291–311). Leiden: Brill.
- Eversteijn, N. (2011). "All at once": *Language choice and codeswitching by Turkish-Dutch teenagers*.
- Kemaloğlu-Er, E. (2018). Patterns of Intrasentential Code-Switching in Turkish-English Bilingual Discourse: Testing the Free Morpheme and the Equivalence Constraint. *Artibilim: Adana Science and Technology University Journal of Social Science* 2018, 1(2), 35–45. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/612458>
- Koban, D. (2013). Intra-sentential and Inter-sentential Code-switching in Turkish-English Bilinguals in New York City, U.S. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 70, 1174–1179. Science Direct. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.01.173>
- Mellado, E. A., & Lignos, C. (2022). *Borrowing or Codeswitching? Annotating for Finer-Grained Distinctions in Language Mixing*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.04973.
- Myers-Scotton, C. (1983). The negotiation of identities in conversation: a theory of markedness and code choice. *International Journal of the sociology of Language* 1983(44), 115-136. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl.1983.44.115>
- Myers-Scotton, C. (2006). *Multiple Voices: An Introduction to Bilingualism*. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Poplack, S. & Dion, N. (2012). Myths and facts about loanword development. *Language variation and change*, 24(3): 279-315.
- Poplack, S. (1980). Sometimes I'll start a sentence in Spanish Y TERMINO EN ESPAÑOL: toward a typology of code-switching. *Linguistics*, 18(7-8). <https://doi.org/10.1515/ling.1980.18.7-8.581>